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**THE GREAT NIZAMI. POET'S LIFE.
PART I**

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Abstract

The year 2021 marks the 900th anniversary of the birth of Nizami Ganjavi. Azerbaijan has the honorable but also challenging task of commemorating this momentous anniversary of the genius Azerbaijani poet in a dignified manner.

Keywords: curious, monograph, talent, literature.

The significance of Nizami's work goes beyond the boundaries of Azerbaijani literature proper. His works are amazing achievement of human genius like works of great masters of the world: Firdausi, Dante, Shakespeare, etc.

We need to make his poems available to all the peoples of our immense planet by the time we celebrate his birth anniversary. This will require a lot of hard work, because, unfortunately, so far not much has been done to avenge the study of Nizami, as in general with regard to the study of the literatures of the East. It is currently impossible to show the entire richness and depth of Nizami's work. It is particularly difficult to do so in a popular presentation, which necessarily requires a long and painstaking research work to precede it.

The present article is one of the first attempts to introduce the life and work of Nizami to a wider audience. Therefore, it cannot aim at solving all the prob-

lems associated with the study of his works. Any attempt at a comprehensive coverage of Nizami's work can be accomplished only in the form of a voluminous monograph, but not in the framework of a journal article. At this stage the task is more modest. I just want to familiarize the readers with the basic facts, to show who Nizami was, what his works consist of and why this work has such an immense value.

The XI-XII centuries A.D. is one of the most tumultuous and turbulent periods in the history of the Near East. If by the beginning of the 10th century the spread of the Caliphate was over and the local dynasties that had departed from it on all fringes were again vigorously trying to occupy the dominant position, then by the beginning of the 11th century the Seljuks, who were moving on their horses with fabulous speed and were everywhere throwing their masters aside, began to influx from the steppes of Central Asia.

The history of these centuries is an unbroken chain of clashes. The local patrimonial aristocracy fights among themselves, ravaging each other's possessions and weakening each other, the Seljuks knock out of the saddle one by one small princes who failed to unite, unite small possessions into a large whole, but, as a result of internal strife, again let them disintegrate into their constituent parts. It can be said that the map of the Near East at that time almost constantly changes its outlines, the boundaries of individual principalities are redrawn almost every year, and, sometimes, for years remain uncertain and fluctuate in one direction or another.

It is curious that this unstable situation, however, not only did not paralyze the literary life of the Near East, but even as if it contributed to the increase in the number of literary figures. The reason for this lies in the nature of the literary life of that era. It should be borne in mind that poetic creativity at that time required mastering an extremely complex poetic technique, without knowledge of which, guided by mere intuition, it was absolutely impossible to write poems. The time input for mastering this technique was usually so great that it was extremely difficult to have any side craft at the same time. Thus, unless a poet was a wealthy man or a dervish sheikh, he had to find a patron at all costs. Such patrons could be found only among the ruling circles, in the ranks of the feudal aristocracy. Consequently, the more feudal courts appeared, the more the country was fragmented, the more hope the poet had of finding a suitable refuge.

Most rulers were quite eager to attract talented poets to their courts. The task of these court singers was, on the one hand, to glorify the real or imagined exploits of their lords, and on the other hand, to entertain them at their feasts with elegant impromptus, passionate ghazals or, at times, rampantly cynical and dirty satires.

The competition at court made the position of such poets not particularly enviable. They had to fight for their place, every handout had to be begged for, and there was always a risk that a competitor would find a more subservient and magnificent hyperbole to glorify the host. As a result, pretended poets often lost all measure in pursuit of payment and fell into hyperbole that contradicted all common sense.

It is not surprising, therefore, that many of the most important representatives of the profession gave up their former activities at the end of their lives and recalled them with the greatest disgust, as work unworthy of a decent man.

The Samanid court was the first to develop in the former Caliphate in the possessions of the Bukhara Samanids, by the beginning of the tenth century. The Samanid court became for many years the model for all the dynasties that emerged in the Near East, and its ceremonialism passed on to the Ghaznavids and later to the Seljuks in the eleventh century. This imitation of the Samanids, enshrined in tradition, led to the selection of Persian as the literary language for this poetry in all corners of the caliphate, a language first widely introduced into the court by the Samanids. The usual gradation is as follows: theology and the sciences, under

strong pressure from it, require the use of Arabic; artistic creation should use the Persian language, while local languages retain the domain of colloquial speech and may be admitted to a very small extent in satirical literature. In other words, a three-degree gradation is created. Although this provision narrowed the already narrow range of consumers of literature, it gave poets and the famous an advantage. By specializing in a local language the poet would be confined to one small area, which could sometimes put him in a completely hopeless position. Using the Persian language, the poet could find a use for himself from the banks of the Ganges to the Mediterranean Sea and from the Syr Darya to Mesopotamia. This situation changed only after the Mongol invasion, when Arabic became a secondary language, the language of science became Persian, and different local languages began to penetrate into literature more and more strongly.

It comes as no surprise, therefore, that even in eleventh-twelfth century Azerbaijan the main literary language was Persian, the only language that had access to the court and which met the requirements of the feudal aristocracy.

Twelfth-century Azerbaijan gives the same picture of fragmentation into separate smaller domains that was so characteristic of the entire former caliphate at this time. Arran with the main city of Ganja, which had been under the rule of the shaddadid dynasty since the middle of the 10th century, was seized by the Seljuks in the second half of the 11th century. Shirvan ruled by dynasty of kesranids from the middle of XII century, atabeks who were governed by Seljuk viceroys with the centre in Ardebil, Meraga and surrounding areas were ruled by atabeks-aksonkorids since 1136.

Of all these rulers, court poetry was most appreciated by the Shirvanshahs, who attracted to their court such major poets of the time as Abu-l-Ala and his pupil Hakani and Falaki. All these three poets, although worked in Shirvan, but were from Ganja. It shows that at that time Ganja was very important place in cultural life of Azerbaijan. It was connected with economic strengthening of Ganja. After the defeat of Berdaa by Russians, Ganja emerged as one of the first cities of "Muslim" Caucasus. Although its position at the junction with the Georgian possessions placed it under the threat of attack, forcing the inhabitants to be always ready to defend themselves, this position had also advantages due to the development of the silk industry. The fact that the city extremely developed and was extremely large centre at that time is shown at least by the mention of the earthquake that befell Ganja in 1138-9, which is still extant among historians. Chronicles state that three hundred or two hundred and thirty thousand people died during this catastrophe. Let us assume that this figure is greatly exaggerated, but even if we reduce it by several times, taking into account that the entire population was exterminated by the earthquake, we would still have to admit that it was a very large city. It was also the birthplace of the poet who was destined to eclipse the glory of his predecessors at the Shirvan court.

Nizamaddin Abu-Muhammad Ilyas ibn Yusif ibn Zeki-Muayyad, known by his poetic pseudonym Nizami, was born in Ganja around 1140-41. There is no information about his origin in the sources. However, one can say with certainty that his family was related to urban population and had nothing to do with feudal aristocracy. Nevertheless, the family must have had a certain amount of wealth, which allowed them to give their sons a brilliant education for their time. Nizami's brother, known as Kiwami Mutarrizi, was also an outstanding poet. Few of his works have survived, but it is clear from the available samples that he mastered the complex technique of poetic skill to the fullest extent. This would not have been possible without extensive training and in-depth study of Arabic and Persian poetry.

Nizami's mother was of Kurdish origin. Therefore, one should think that from an early age Nizami already had a good command of at least two languages - a circumstance which was very good for the development of linguistic sensitivity and facilitated learning new languages later on.

Nizami was orphaned at an early age and left in the care of his mother, who did everything possible to broaden her son's education. We do not know where Nizami studied. We can only say that he was well versed in all areas of science at the time. His works show a very deep knowledge of philosophy, astronomy and medicine. This knowledge could only have been acquired with perfect mastery of the Persian language as well as Arabic. The poetic technique of Nizami shows that, apart from the sciences, he also paid enormous attention to poetry, both Persian and Arabic.

A comparison of the dates preserved in the sources shows that Nizami got married rather late, not earlier than 26-27 years old. In 1174-1175 he had a son - Muhammad whom the poet loved a lot. He had a son - Muhammad, whom the poet loved very much. The relations between the father and son were friendly. The father initiated him into his creative plans and reckoned with his advice. It was only thanks to the persuasion of the fourteen-year-old Mohammed that Nizami undertook to develop a novel about Majnun and created one of his remarkable works. It is quite possible that this passionate love of Nizami for Muhammad grew from the fact that soon after his birth Nizami lost his first wife. Judging by the lines dedicated to her in one of his poems, the poet always remembered her with deep sorrow. After her death, Nizami married again, but soon lost his second wife. Only with the third one he was destined to live a long life. It is noteworthy that Nizami did not exercise his right to have several wives at the same time throughout his life. Of course, it could be explained by the lack of necessary material resources. However, his poems clearly show the deep respect he had for women. Contrary to the views of ruling circles, for him a woman was not a commodity to be bought for fun or to run a household. A woman, in his eyes, was a

faithful companion who helped a man in his work and inspired him to all sorts of exploits.

Having studied the sciences, to which the existence of scholarly writings gave access, Nizami did not stop there. The official orthodoxy apparently did not fully satisfy him. He sought to get even closer to the truth he was seeking. This quest led him into the circles of Sufi sheikhs. We do not know to what extent Sufi teachings satisfied him. It should be thought that at least the known freedom of views of Sufism, the fact that Sufism did not always regard Muslim orthodoxy alone as the only possible way to the truth, should have made a great impression on Nizami. Living in a frontier town, confronted in everyday life with representatives of various ethnicities, Nizami managed early on to transcend narrow national boundaries. As we will see further, he portrays representatives of almost all nations known to him, and to all of them he approaches with great objectivity, trying to emphasize positive features. It is possible that such views were to a certain extent strengthened by the influence of those Sufi circles with which he had become intimate. He was adopted into Sufi circles by a certain Sheikh Ahi Farrukh Zenjani. Unfortunately, we do not know anything about this sheikh. However, his title - Ahi, which seems to indicate his connection with the Anatolian Ahi movement, which had played a great role in the history of the Near East, deserves attention. Ahi continued to some extent the Futuvva movement, the secret organisations whose task was to protect the rights of urban artisans. The Ahi movement had serious consequences, such as the famous Bedreddin Simavi rebellion. In other words, of all the many Sufi organisations, this was one of the most active, not inclined to confine itself to passive contemplation alone, and sometimes able to raise the masses to struggle against the exploiters. Nizami's association with this sheikh further underlines the poet's closeness to the urban population. It is clear that this environment with its teachings of the need to help the needy and oppressed allowed Nizami's great humanism to develop. Here he could learn to see the injustice of the existing state and to penetrate into the innermost recesses of human hearts with an inquisitive gaze, unraveling their innermost motivations.

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